

THE GOAL AND TASK OF DEVELOPING MORAL-CULTURAL RELATIONS AMONG TEACHERS

Termez State Pedagogical Institute
Department of Preschool Education
Lecturer: **G‘aniyeva Sayyora**

Annotation: This article considers the urgent issue of developing professional, ethical and cultural relations in students of pedagogical specialties who are future teachers. The authors emphasize that the development of teachers as individuals capable not only of imparting knowledge, but also of instilling in their students moral values and respect for cultural diversity directly depends on the quality of their moral and cultural preparation. The article analyzes the main components of moral relations, such as responsibility, honesty, justice and respect for each student, as well as cultural relations such as tolerance, intercultural competence and appreciation of cultural heritage. It considers the impact of these relations on teaching, creating a favorable educational environment and developing a civic position in the younger generation.

Keywords: professional ethics, moral values, tolerance, intercultural competence, respect for the individual, responsibility, justice, cultural heritage, civic position

The student-youth group constitutes an independent and very important part of the group in which moral culture should be developed[108]. In some cases, this moral culture acquires a marginal character in relation to society, in which cases of deviation from generally recognized norms of behavior can be observed.

Moral culture is the process of comprehensively developing a person, shaping his consciousness, behavior and worldview on the basis of a specific, specific goal and socio-historical experience. In another interpretation, education is a process of activity aimed at comprehensively raising the younger generation towards a specific goal, shaping social consciousness and behavior in it[56].

Also, the content of national morality is formed by the verses of the Holy Quran, the Hadiths of the Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him), national-cultural values, folk pedagogy, and the works of thinkers and scientists on education.

At different stages of historical development, the essence of morality is different, and its content is based on social goals. Although the idea of moral culture is expressed differently, it expresses unity in terms of its nature and object of orientation.

The process of developing moral and cultural relations in future teachers should be the result of a pedagogical process aimed at preparing them as individuals capable of serving our independent state and people with loyalty, patriots, universal and national moral values.

The process of developing moral and cultural relations in future teachers is a process of organized and goal-oriented cooperation between teachers and students (educators and students). In this process, the consciousness of the student is formed, his feelings develop, and behavioral habits are formed that serve to organize social relations necessary for social life.

In the process of developing moral and cultural relations in future teachers, it is necessary to cultivate not only the minds of future teachers, but also their feelings, to form in them behavioral skills and habits that correspond to the moral requirements of society for the individual. To achieve this, the mind, feelings and will of the student are influenced. If any of these are neglected, it becomes difficult to achieve the goal. Organizing the educational process on the basis of cooperation between teachers and future teachers is a factor in its effectiveness. In this regard, it is important to create the necessary conditions for the effective organization of cooperation.

Active participation in the spiritual and social processes of the university increases the independence and creative initiative of future teachers.

By organizing the processes based on the interests and desires of the team of future teachers, their self-awareness process occurs. When a student becomes responsible for his behavior and actions before the team, he becomes not an executor, but an active participant in the common cause.

In order to effectively establish the process of developing moral and cultural relations in future teachers, it is important to know and take into account its driving force, source. This consists of internal and external factors affecting the process of education and upbringing.

In developing moral and cultural relations in future teachers, it is also necessary to take into account their level of upbringing. If this aspect is forgotten, certain contradictions arise. The skills and habits formed in the process of activity facilitate compliance with moral standards.

Therefore, it is important for a science teacher to have a special influence on the student's mind during the student years, a period of rapid development of the student's personality, through various activities (study, work, social work, games, sports, artistic hobbies). Otherwise, as a result of a poor understanding of the norms of behavior and

moral requirements, the individual may become unstable in social relations and susceptible to random influences[67].

Moral education is of particular importance in the educational process of higher education institutions. The tasks set for the comprehensive development of the personality of future teachers, effective management, control, and evaluation of processes are solved not through random actions, but on the basis of predetermined and well-thought-out plans. In the process of developing moral and cultural relations, its goals, forms, and methods, as well as the reflexive aspects of the individual, i.e. self-education and re-education, play an important role. The content of the process of developing moral and cultural relations is determined by the state and society, and certain conditions are required for its implementation. These ideas are reflected in a holistic way as follows:

The process of developing moral and cultural relations of young people is organized on the basis of a specific goal. The goal of the process of developing moral and cultural relations is determined based on the development of society, its direction of development, and the content of social relations. Today, the main goal of the internal regulations and code of ethics in higher educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan is to train a modern, independent-minded, patriotic, professionally competent specialist.

The result of the process of developing moral and cultural relations is the education of highly qualified personnel who meet high spiritual and ethical requirements. This process is two-way and requires organization and leadership, management, as well as activity on the part of the student himself. The cooperation of the teacher and future teachers plays a leading role in this process. As a result, future teachers understand the essence of the general goals of social education, practically master the implementation of the system of tasks carried out towards the goal, the selection of forms, methods and means of developing moral and cultural relations in a reasonable and scientific manner and their application in practice. The essence of the process of developing moral and cultural relations can be clarified by analyzing this process based on various approaches.

The moral qualities of a person are formed as a result of education and upbringing. The moral and cultural relations of a person are also closely interconnected. In the process of developing moral-cultural relations, the student's personality develops not in parts, but as a whole[76]. As the student grows and develops, the tasks of education become more complex, deepen, and stratify.

In order to develop moral-cultural relations in future teachers, it is advisable to consistently influence their minds and feelings, provide intellectual, ideological-political, moral, labor, aesthetic, physical, ecological, economic, and ethical education, ensure the unity of the minds, behavior, and activities of future teachers, as well as implement pedagogical technologies that ensure the integration of individual, group, and mass forms of this process, and use innovative methods, forms, and tools.

References

1. Begmatov A. Spiritual philosophy or the creation of a new philosophical system in the works of Islam Karimov. –T.: Sharq, 2000. -94 p.
2. Bobokhonov Sh., Irisov A. Leaders of the science of Hadith. –Tashkent: Nur, 1992. -72 p.
3. National program for the promotion of moral culture in society.\\ Bulletin of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan. 1998. Issue 8, p. 23-33.
4. Nasriddinova O.T. Moral culture is important in the formation of civil society (on the example of youth). Dissertation for the degree of candidate of legal sciences. -T: 2009.- 36 p.
5. Ganieva, S.S. "Historical Analysis of the Spiritual and Moral Education of Students Based on Value Theories." "Economy and Society," 2024, pp. 166-168.
6. Ganieva, S.S. "Historical Analysis of the Spiritual and Moral Education of Students Based on Value Theories." Journal of Education, Science, and Innovation, 2024, No. 5, pp. 411–414.

Research Science and Innovation House

